

QUIZ**LAST NAME: IWUOHA****FIRST NAME: CHINAZOM****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What two citation formats are used in the Turabian rule of style?**

- Note-Bibliography Style and Author-Date Style.¹**
- Author-Bibliography Style and Note-Date Style.
- Note-Author Style and Bibliography-Date Style.
- None of the above.

2. **A block quote of five or more lines should include ALL the following EXCEPT:**

- Be single-spaced.

1. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers., Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

- Add quotation marks at the beginning and end of the blockquote.²**
- Leave a blank line before and after the blockquote.
- Not include quotation marks at the beginning or end of the blockquote.
3. **What is the general rule when placing the second set of double quotes around a passage enclosed in double quotes?**
- No Change. Enclose a set of double quotes around another set of double quotes.
- Enclose a set of single quotes around the entire passage.
- Keep the external double quotes and change the internal quotes to single quotation marks.³**
- Enclose a set of double quotes around the entire passage.
4. **The following are the importance of paraphrasing EXCEPT:**
- Authors may use exact information enclosed in quotes and may skip citing the work.⁴**
- The writing style must express the author's ideas in a different style than the author used and represent the author's original writing accurately.
- It allows authors to gather and express their topic ideas or information in their own words.

2. Ibid., 209.

3. Ibid.

4. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 8.

5. **What are the basic footnote and proper italicization format?**
- Authors Name. Date. *Book Title*. Place of Publication: Publisher.⁵**
 - Authors Name. *Book Title*. Date. Place of Publication: Publisher.
 - Authors Name. Date. Book Title. *Place of Publication: Publisher*.
 - Authors Name*. Book Title. *Date*. Place of Publication: Publisher.
6. **When writing a research paper, the following spacing and margin rules apply EXCEPT:**
- Maintain a one-inch margin around the four sides of each page.
 - Use the tab key set to five spaces to indent the first line of each paragraph and leave only one space after a period.
 - There are no rules for setting margins or indenting a new paragraph.⁶**
 - Avoid placing headings, hyphenated words, and new paragraphs at the bottom of the page.
7. **The following statements are true about when NOT to provide citation:**
- When authors express their own original ideas, theories, arguments, or conclusion.
 - When surveys and experiments are designed and carried out by the author.
 - When authors develop their own research method and convey common knowledge.

5. Ibid., 12

6. Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 27.

All the above.⁷

8. **Plagiarism is when an author does the following:**

Reference ideas only.

Reference quotes only.

Neglects to reference ideas, quotes, or any other materials that have been used from a source.⁸

Reference ideas and quotes only.

9. **How is an ellipsis used according to the University of Oxford Style Guide?**

Use an ellipsis to show that some text is missing, usually from a quotation.⁹

Add square brackets around an ellipsis.

Do not use an ellipsis to indicate a trailing off in speech or thought.

Ellipsis must be used at least once in every research paper.

10. **According to the WHO Style Guide, abbreviations may be formed in which of the following ways:**

By removing the end of a word and replacing it with a full stop (i.e., Jan., Co.).

7. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 57.

8. Ibid.

9. Ibid., 88.

- By removing the middle of a word, a full stop is not generally required, (i.e., Dr, Mr).
- By joining the first letters of main words or parts of words, as in titles of organizations (i.e., WHO - World Health Organization).
- All the above.**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.
- Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

10. World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. (Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 3.